

Using Geomarketing to select the best site for a new hypermarket in Northern Riyadh

Zouheir Sallman¹, Fathoni Usman²

¹College of Graduate as Studies, Universiti Tenaga Nasional, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

²Institute of Energy Infrastructure, Universiti Tenaga Nasional, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.

Abstract: In this paper the determine of the best location for a new commercial retail using geographic information systems is presented by studying several factors. The most important of which is determining the population density based on the use of high-resolution satellite images in order to know the existing residential buildings and determining the population in the study area based on the number and residential buildings type in the study area which is located in the northern part of the Riyadh City. Spot 6, with a 1.5 m resolution with ARC GIS 10.1 are used to determine the existing residential buildings to expect the population at micro-geographic area which will analysed by geomarketing tools to identify the suitable location of hypermarket. This study can be developed for use in other areas such as environmental studies and health as well.

Keywords: GIS, Best site location, population, Geomarketing, remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Spatial information plays the key factor for new business or establish a new facility [1]. For that, the decision for open new hypermarket with a specific condition is a critical decision for its financial impact and risk that have to consider during the process of the selection. For this reason, effective research must be undertaken with a successful scenario design to avoid any problems that may arise in the future.

In general, establish a new business mean a new location to start working which will necessary the use Geoinformation and GIS because of its the system that able to work and analysis with this type of data and the ability to imagine the suitable scenario to support the decision-makers during the select a new location, [2]. The Capacity and ability of GIS is very important in the decision-making process especially for the people who have not enough knowledge of the spatial data [3], also the ability to deal with the big data and link it with thematic and digital maps to the database, all those GIS and Geoinformation features make it the cornerstone in this site selection process.

The factors that have an impact on the decision making is population, competitors, and Land price, therefore we will study and analyse those factors and its impacts. To conduct like this study, the decision makers usually use many criteria and ways to have more models and alternatives solutions, one of the is (AHP) which designed to prepare a breakdown for the problem that needs to solve it [4]. ArcGIS analysis was used in this study to select the best site location for a new hypermarket in the study area, selected the factors that have an impact on the study and priorities it according to specific criteria then converted those layers to raster to process it by using raster calculators.

2 Literature Review

The geographic information system has the ability to combine spatial data, especially competitor sites, with solutions designed to help open a new facility to enhance the competitiveness of the new entity. Competitive sites consist of several criteria and are primarily related to consumers and service providers. Here, customer behaviour must be considered so that we can meet their demands so that they can have all their requirements in one place [5]. The opening of a new branch for any company or service is one of the critical works that requires careful study and depends on scientific methodologies in which the study of the situation in various aspects to mitigate any risks that may result from the expansion of activity.

The population density that will be used to determine the new location has been studied based on the data obtained from the Statistics Authority [6]. Qiming noted that the opening of a new branch for any company is an important decision that should be considered carefully. He described the problem and presented solutions and suggestions to guide users to find the best site. Initially, he suggested a solution without looking at the competitors and then propose another solution, considering the threat resulting from competitor's activities, he used GIS to be designing and study these solutions [7]. Xuefeng used ArcGIS Geoprocessing to develop spatial analysis modelling and decision making by using implementation technology, modelling and multiple options using ARC GIS, using the classification and reclassification method, and calculating the required spaces to set up the new branch within the conditions and result [8]. In other area, Kazem presented a study to select the best location for parking as a result of the traffic jam of Tehran city and presented the study of land use and peak areas of traffic and restrictions that prevent the establishment of this position such as cultural restrictions and historical monuments, all those features have been added all to the maps to determine the outputs that correspond with Determine the best location for parking [9].

3 Study Area

The study area is located in the northern part of the of Riyadh city, the capital of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. It is characterized by high urban activity and an area of about 240 square kilometres. The study area has been divided into small districts or Micro-Geographic areas, which helps to conduct detailed studies.

4 Methodology

The process of selecting a new hypermarket or retail location starting by determining the Vacant land with a minimum required area, then selected which is close to the main roads, the land price will consider in this study with the distance to the competitors and the population density, All those factors will process by Arc GIS, Finally the results will classify according to its priority.

4.1 Work Flow

The main road obtained by using open street maps while the vacant land digitized by using high-resolution satellite images (Image date January 2016) which also used to extract the existing buildings and classified it according to its buildings type to calculate the population in the studying area at districts level or Micro-Geographic area. The total number of residential buildings with its type (villa, building, and palace) and the number of housing units in each of these buildings will be determined according to the data of the Saudi Statistics Authority. Hence, depending on the same data, the number of residents in each housing unit will be known. In each district and then estimate the population in the study area as a whole. ArcGIS will be used to analyse and determine the total population in the study area at the level of small residential blocks.

Figure 1 work flow

4.1.1 Land Price

The land price will constrain the new investments and therefore it is considered an influential factor due to the high value of land in the Riyadh city, which is the highest in the region and here will be divided study area districts to a segmentation that reflect the land value segmentations. The land value is determined in many ways, including:

- a. Distance to the main roads where the land value rises.
- b. Distance to the city centre which the prices in downtown is highest.

Figure 1 shows the land price (value) calcification according to the previous three points, the Red colour is the highest price segmentation while the dark blue is the lowest segmentation. The highest segmentation located beside the main two roads (Northern road and King Abdul Al Aziz Road) and between King Abdul Al Aziz Road and King Fahed Road.

Figure 2: Land price classification

4.1.2 Population

Determine the building type will be valuable for urban area planning and improve business, in other meaning, remote sensing will give us new tool by identifying the population in the districts and micro-geographic area by having information about the total Buildings with its geospatial information, so the buildings will give us the reading and indicator for the population. By using the geospatial data, we will be able to have more accurate information about the population in the studying area and market needs at districts level. Population information will support decision makers in many sectors (i.e. governmental and business) to have the right decision depending on the new data.

The total Buildings in January 2016 was 50243 buildings, the residential buildings were 48225 (95.98 % from total). According to the 2013 census (Authority of statics) in KSA:

- The average units per villa is 3.5 units. (V)
 - The average units per Apartment is 15.5 units. (A)
 - The average units per palace is 1 unit. (P)
 - The average population per units is 5.97 person per units. (AVE)
 - Percentage of non-inhabited buildings in Riyadh is 12 % (88% inhabited). (E).
- Depend on 2013 census that in general, the ground floor in villas is occupied by a Saudi family which have a driver and housekeeper at 50%.

Population in a villa

$$POP VI = (V*AVE) + [(driver + housekeeper) * 50\%] * E \quad 1$$

$$POP VI = (3.5 * 5.97) + [(driver + housekeeper) * 50\%] * 88\% = 19.26 \text{ person}$$

38 % of Apartments population is Saudi (25% of this Saudi segment has a housekeeper).

Population in Apartment

$$POPAPA = \{(A*AVE) + [(A*AVE) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * E \quad 2$$

$$POPAPA = \{(15.5*5.97) + [(15.5*5.98) * 38\%] * 25\% \} * 88\% = (92.69 + 8.790825) * 88\% = 89.16 \text{ person}$$

Population in Palace

$$POP PA = (P*AVE) + (Driver + housekeeper + cooker + gardener) * E \quad 3$$

$$POP PA = (1*5.97) + (Driver + housekeeper + cooker + gardener) * 88\% = (5.98 + 4)*88\% = 8.77 \text{ person.}$$

Table 1: Average number of units per residential type and its population

Building type	Average No. units	Average population per building type
Apartment	15.5	89.16
Villa	3.5	19.26
Palace	1	8.77

The residential buildings that extracted by January 2016 satellite images are shown in the Table 2. It explains the number of residential buildings with the average population in those building according to building type. This estimation depends on the Table 1.

Table 2: Expected population in the study area according to building type

Building type	No. of building	Average population per building type (person)	Total population (person)
Villa	44603	19.2676	859392
Apartment	3345	89.16672	298262
Palace	277	8.7809	2432
		Sum	1160086

Now, we will search where those people lives? In which district? Where the highest population which will mark as the highest potential market size. GIS will help to give each building the district code which located in, here will know how much buildings in each district and how much people in each district. This methodology will help the decision makers to have a good view an about the expected demand in the area and change their plan accordingly.

Figure 2: Expected Population at January 2016

Figure 2 shows the expected population according to January. The Districts with dark blue are the highest population density while the red colour reflects the lowest. This factor is most important because people who will do the business, purchase and visited retail sites, therefore, a new way of finding out the population density has to be found. So, as we have seen, satellite imagery has helped us detect new and old buildings and calculate the population in areas better than other methods, which depend on tables or other method.

We studied the population in this research and calculated the estimation at districts level to know which places people live? Here, the area with high population density will be attractive places for investment and establish new activities. By using ARC GIS the population data converted to population density. Figure 3 will guide the process to target the areas with high population density and give it high priorities. In Figure 3 the dark blue reflects the high density which has the number (1) in the legend. Also, the population who lives in the buildings which scanned in January 2016 will be taking into account

Figure 3: population density

4.1.2 Land Use

Land uses map was created by using the Spot 6 satellite image to distinguish the lands to take it in our account and avoid it. This classification includes as in Figure 4 which are garden, mall, palaces, unknown area and industry.

Figure 4: Land use

4.1.4 Competitors

When you create an activity that requires careful study of the market. So that the proposed activity should be away from competitors in a way that provides the right investment away from conflicts of interest with them, taking the current competitors and creating a map showing the distance to the competitors must be taken into account which is beneficial for investment.

The choice of the best site based on the required conditions will be more accurate by using remote sensing and Geomarketing, which provides the possibility of dealing with the places through equations given to the computer according to the required factors to give a number of suggested sites that are compatible to the criteria for the establishment of sites required. Field survey for the Retail Stores in the study area was conducted to identify the competitors. The search included the branded stores and did not include the hundreds of small stores in the districts, this search was

done in two ways (i.e. field visit and stores websites). The information that recorded, only retail market name and its location the following stores were recorded in the study area as listed in Table 3. While Figure 5 shows the map of retails location in the study area.

Table 3: the retails in the study area

Retail brand	number of retails
Aljazeera	1
Al-Sadhan	1
Panda	19
Carrefour	2
Danube	4
Otahaim	7
Tamimi	8

Figure 5: Retails (competitors) location in the study area

4.1.5 Land Area

This stage is a complex process, it depends on dropping the sites of buildings, roads, and land use, by using ArcGIS the results are the lands which has not any activities. Here only the land which has enough area to build the retail building will consider, in Riyadh city the average area for the Malls is 20000 Meter square for that only the land with an area more than 20000 m² will talk it into account. Figure 6 shows that the blue color is the highest land space.

Figure 6: Empty land in the study area

4.1.6 Select the Best new Hypermarket Location

After processing and preparing the required layers we will be able to start by selecting the suitable sites for that. The required layers will convert to rasters then reclassify, the results are rasters which will analyses by raster calculators in ARC GIS. Those rasters will weight as the following:

- Land price weight is 15 %
- Distance to current market 25 %
- Population density weight 60 %

The results of the raster calculators are shown as a raster in Figure 7. In this map, light blue (i.e. number 1 in the legend) reflect the high priority.

Figure 7: raster calculation

The results will be a raster, by converting it to layer and by taking the intersection with empty lands in Figure 6. in Figure 7 the highest priority in the legend is number 1 while the lowest is number 5, and we take into account the flowing at this stage: the distance to main road is less than 100 meters and keep only the priority number one and two. The result is the best site location for new retails by considering the previous criteria as presented in Figure 8. Total number of suitable places is 20 sites. Table 4 explain the suitable places with its area.

Figure 8: The best site locations

Table 4: List of best vacant land for a new hypermarket

Id	Area (m ²)
1	20362
2	20406
3	21994
4	22362
5	23245
6	24604
7	25994
8	26874
9	27791
10	28027
11	28384
12	28800
13	30108
14	33133
15	33461
16	33843
17	33905
18	34481
19	35538
20	46402

4.1.7 Conclusion

We saw how the using of remote sensing provide us with necessary tools to help us to understand and improve our planning, increase the benefits of using it in industry. The high-resolution satellite images have provided what can be said as a qualitative leap in the search and put the science in the service of the community and the business world.

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